

Engineering defect clustering in diamond-based materials for technological applications via quantum-mechanical descriptors

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Dopant-dopant and dopant-vacancy complexes in diamond can be exploited for the development of quantum computers, single-photon emitters, high-precision magnetic field sensing and nanophotonic devices. While some dopant-vacancy complexes such as nitrogen- and silicon-vacancy centres are well-studied, studies of other dopant/vacancy clusters are focused mainly on defect detection, with minimal investigation into their electronic features or how to tune their electronic and optical properties for specific applications. To this aim, we perform a thorough analysis of the coupled structural and electronic features of different dopant-dopant and dopant-vacancy cluster defects in diamond by means of first principle calculations. We find that doping with *p-type* (*n-type*) dopant does not always lead to the creation of *p-type* (*n-type*) diamond structures, depending on the kind of cluster defect. We also identify quantum mechanical descriptors which are most suitable to tune the electronic band gap about the Fermi level for each defect type. Finally, we propose how to choose suitable dopant atomic types, concentration and geometric environments, to fabricate diamond-based materials for several technological applications such as electrodes, transparent conductive materials, intermediate band photovoltaics and multicolour emitters among others.

Keywords: Diamond, Doping, Vacancies, Impurities, Defect clustering, Band structure, Intermediate band photovoltaics, Degenerate semiconductor

I. INTRODUCTION

The unique set of extreme physical properties such as large thermal conductivity, carrier mobility, ultra-wide band gap, high breakdown field strength, chemical inertness and radiation hardness make diamond an ideal candidate material to reach for in demanding applications [1–5]. These applications include high-frequency FETs [6] and BJTs [7], high-power high-frequency radio signal amplification [8], high-power Schottky and PiN diodes [9–11], switches [1, 3], inert electrodes [4] and radiation sensors [5]. Moreover, diamond’s qualities are of particular importance for both electric transmission and generation in the future electric power systems. The high-power switches and rectifiers [12] are essential for renewable-energy dominated electrical grids, while nuclear fusion industry (e.g. UV photovoltaic cells [13] and nuclear fuel production [14]) as well as solar photovoltaic cells [15, 16] can largely benefit from diamond-based materials. To achieve the diamond’s desired electronic or optical properties, it is necessary to tune its band gap about the Fermi level suitably. Depending on the specific application, we need to adjust the valence and conduction band edges or insert impurity bands into the band gap; the most common way to realise this is by introducing impurities (i.e. doping) into the pristine structure. Artificial diamond has been successfully doped in high concentrations by Al [17], B [18] and P [19], while doping by many other dopant atoms such as Ge [20], Si [21], As [22], N [23],

S [24], Mo and W [25] was experimentally proved to be feasible. Recently, significant attention was given to the colour centres in diamond, mostly dopant-vacancy (X-V) complexes, as they seem crucial for further development of quantum computers, single-photon emitters, as well as of high-precision magnetic field sensing, nanophotonic, optomechanic and plasmonic devices [26–34]. The colour centres can be created during chemical vapour deposition and high pressure, high temperature (HPHT) processes or by ion incorporation followed by thermal or HPHT annealing, depending on the dopant atomic type and desired application [21, 26, 28, 35–37]. Other defects created by the aggregation of dopants and/or vacancies are dopants as nearest neighbours, dopants as near-nearest neighbours and dopants aggregated around the vacancy, named X-X, X-C_n-X and X_n-V, respectively, where *n* corresponds to the number of carbon atoms between two dopants and dopants enclosing a vacancy [38–40]. All of these cluster defects containing nitrogen have been successfully created with suitable annealing conditions [40, 41]. Moreover, clustering of impurities has been observed in systems doped by boron [42] or phosphorus [43], especially at high dopant concentrations. Studies focused on cluster defects other than X-V complexes are mostly dedicated to the calculation of defect formation and binding energies, impurity levels, or to the different methods of defect detection in the sample [44–50]. In addition, the formation of cluster defects is often seen as unwanted [42], and their possible role in technological applications is overlooked.

In this context, we attempt to reveal coupled structural-electronic features of different dopant/vacancy configurations and their effect on the band gap of diamond-derived materials. We conduct a quantum me-

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chanical investigation of diamond-based structures containing different types of cluster defects and dopant atoms in different concentrations. We suggest how to choose suitable dopant atomic types, concentration and kind of aggregation to achieve the target electrical or optical effect. Finally, we discuss how the different cluster defects can be exploited in several technological applications such as transparent conductive materials, laser diodes, intermediate band photovoltaics and multi-colour emitters.

II. COMPUTATIONAL DETAILS

We conduct our simulations in the framework of the Density Functional Theory with Projected Augmented-Wave (PAW) pseudopotentials as implemented in the ABINIT package [51–54]. According to previous studies [55, 56], we select the GGA-WC energy functional [57] for all of our simulations, as it reproduces the lattice parameters and the width of the band gap of the pristine diamond with a good agreement. The energy cutoff for the plane wave basis set is chosen to be 1633 eV, with a corresponding 3265 eV cutoff for the PAW double grid. The sampling of the Brillouin zone is done within the Monkhorst-Pack scheme [58], and is scaled according to the size of the unit cell, by using a $21 \times 21 \times 21$ mesh for the pristine diamond and a $11 \times 11 \times 11$ mesh for the smallest doped structure. The Self-Consistent Field is considered to achieve convergence when the energy difference between two subsequent iterations is below 10^{-11} eV. To obtain ground-state structural models, we perform geometry optimization cycles until the largest component of the forces acting on the atoms is smaller than 5×10^{-6} eV/Å. By using these settings, the geometry optimisation of the pristine diamond model yielded a lattice parameter equal to 3.561 Å, which is consistent with the experimental value of 3.567 Å [55]. The calculated band gap size is 4.14 eV, in agreement with already reported DFT calculations [59]. Such value is smaller than the experimental value of 5.47 eV as reported in previous studies [1, 2]; indeed, it is known that DFT underestimates the band gap width [60]. However, in the forthcoming discussion, we are interested in relative variations of the electronic features with respect to the ground-state model of the pristine diamond structure; such relative variations are then not affected by the difference in the calculated band gap value with respect to the experimental one. This has already been shown in a previous computational work [56] which compares the results obtained with different energy functionals including the hybrid HSE06 [61–63]. Due to the same reasons, we conduct calculations without spin polarisation. We are aware that band spin-splitting occurs in the case of X-V complexes and in diamond containing vacancies [64–66]. To assess potential differences between spin-polarised and non-polarised calculations, we conduct benchmark spin-polarised calculations for a single concentration of the X-V defect (1.85

%) with spin magnetisation set to $1.0 \mu_B$ ($S = 1/2$). The results show that the geometry changes are minimal, as interatomic distances between dopants and neighbouring carbons do not change more than 0.01 Å. The most significant difference in the electronic structure is found in the systems where the dopant and its neighbouring carbon atoms form trigonal pyramidal configurations (see B- and N-doped cases in section III B). In these cases, the maximal shift in the position of the impurity bands is 0.3 eV, while for systems with octahedral configuration (Al, P, Si) the shift is smaller, about 0.1 eV (see Table II). As we will see in the following discussion, these differences do not affect the overall trends we are addressing. We perform calculations of defects in neutral charge states, although we acknowledge that defects can exist in their charged states. However, we emphasise that there is inherently no reason for such states to form in a sample doped exclusively with the considered defect and in the absence of external influences. Charged defects are likely to form when additional, often unintended doping is present. For instance, Al-V⁻ and B-V⁻ defects may form in the presence of *n-type* impurities, such as single N or P atoms, in sufficient quantities. Similarly, external factors, such as applying voltage or light illumination, can induce charged defects [40, 67, 68]. Conversely, some charged defects, such as N-V⁻ or Si-V⁻, are often desirable for applications in quantum computing or quantum sensing [30, 40, 69, 70]. Similarly to spin-polarisation, we assume that X-V defects are prone to form charged defects. This arises from their partially filled impurity bands as a result of the presence of dangling bonds. Furthermore, charged X-V defects are the most discussed charged defects in literature, enabling validation of the results of our benchmark. The analysis of charged states is included in section III B. As shown there, the observed trends prove that adding and removing electrons from the defect affects the electronic features in a consistent way. Consequently, we do not anticipate deviations in the trends that we are addressing in our analysis when comparing equivalent charge states of different dopant atomic types.

In order to analyse how the introduction of the different cluster defects alters the electronic properties of the pristine diamond, we consider a large diversity of systems varying in dopant atomic type, concentration and cluster defect type. To consider both *electron acceptors* and *electron donors* (i.e. *p-type* and *n-type* dopants, respectively), we choose five p-block atomic dopant types, namely Al, B, N, P and isovalent Si. However, as we shall see later in the discussion, when considering cluster defects, doping with *p-type* (*n-type*) dopant does not ensure the creation of *p-type* (*n-type*) diamond structure. In order to create the model geometries representing different dopant concentrations, we first considered $2 \times 2 \times 2$, $3 \times 3 \times 3$, $4 \times 4 \times 4$ and $5 \times 5 \times 5$ supercells of the pristine diamond structure, where one carbon atom is substituted with a dopant one; these geometries represent a dopant concentration equal to 6.25%, 1.85%, 0.78% and

0.4%, respectively. For each of such models, we consider the following cases: *a*) we remove one carbon next to the already substituted dopant, thus creating the -X-V model structure with a dopant and a vacancy as nearest neighbours (Figure 1a), *b*) we substitute one carbon next to the dopant with a dopant of the same atomic type, thus creating the -X-X model structure with two dopant atoms as first neighbours (Figure 1b), *c*) we substitute one carbon that is in the second coordination sphere of the dopant with a dopant, thus creating the -X-C-X model (Figure 1c). Moreover, after obtaining the relaxed geometries of the X-C-X models, we remove the carbon atom bonding with the two dopants, thus creating the X-V-X models (Figure 1d), where a vacancy is introduced between two dopant atoms. We also consider diamonds solely with one vacancy as reference structures; we name these model geometries as V. The atomic positions and lattice parameters of all the model geometries have been optimised and used to calculate the electronic properties discussed in the following sections. In what follows, we refer to the concentration of the defect as a whole, regardless the number of dopant atoms needed to form it; for example, $5 \times 5 \times 5$ supercells, which are formed by 250 atoms, then represent a defect concentration equal to $1/250 = 0.4\%$. We name the generic models as $Z-n-d$, where Z is the atomic type of the dopant, n is the multiplicity of the supercell and d is the defect type ($d = X-V, X-X, X-C-X, X-V-X$). For instance, the structure labelled as Al-4-X-X corresponds to a 128-atom supercell with two neighbouring carbon atoms substituted by aluminium. An example of the primitive unit cell of the X-4-X-X system is shown in Figure 2. We emphasise that, to keep the computational load reasonable, we build the models by *i*) assuming an ordered distribution of the defects, and *ii*) considering not too low dopant concentrations. However, we recall that the lowest concentrations here considered are achievable with a single dopant defect (Al [17], B [18], and P [19]), and cluster defects are often formed naturally at high dopant concentrations [42, 43]; this is supported by our formation and binding energy calculations reported in section III. Moreover, as we will see, the features which we inspect in this work, such as the positions of the impurity electronic bands within the band gap and values of the quantum mechanical descriptors, do not change significantly when the concentration is reduced from 0.78 % to 0.4 %. Consequently, we may assume that these features would not change substantially with a further decrease in defect concentration. While it is true that experimental concentrations are often lower, we believe that a 0.4 % concentration can adequately represent them without introducing significant inaccuracies to observed trends and values.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

FIG. 1. Schematic showing considered cluster defects: (a) X-V, (b) X-X, (c) X-C-X and (d) X-V-X.

FIG. 2. Example of the primitive unit cell corresponding to the X-4-X-X system. The blue spheres represent the dopant atom while the brown spheres indicate the position of the carbon atoms.

In the following discussion, we will look at the different cluster defect types separately. In the first subsection, we will describe the methods used in each type of analysis and we will examine the general features common to all defects. Then, we will investigate each defect type from the point of view of their geometry, and electronic structure, and finally, we will consider different quantum mechanical descriptors and their effect on the band gap size. We will see that in many cases geometric and electronic features depend on the atomic radii of the doping atoms. This is especially noticeable when we compare dopants from different periods of the periodic table. To make an easy distinction, we will refer to the period 2 elements B and N as *small dopant atoms* and to the period 3 elements Al, Si and P as *large dopant atoms*.

To provide a preliminary guideline for the experimental synthesis of diamonds containing cluster defects, we calculate the formation energies for each considered defect type, dopant atomic type and concentration. While more comprehensive insights could be gained from phase diagram calculations at different temperatures and pres-

	Defect formation energy E^f				Binding energy E^b			
	6.25%	1.85%	0.78%	0.4%	6.25%	1.85%	0.78%	0.4%
Al	6.09	5.81	5.81	5.83				
X	6.09	5.81	5.81	5.83				
X-V	2.73	4.58	4.86	4.93	-8.81	-7.45	-7.75	-7.97
X-X	6.46	8.69	9.13	9.26	-5.73	-2.93	-2.48	-2.41
X-C-X	6.36	9.57	10.00	10.14	-5.82	-2.06	-1.62	-1.52
X-V-X	4.73	7.21	7.24	7.22	-12.91	-10.64	-11.18	-11.52
B								
X	1.79	1.48	1.39	1.36				
X-V	4.61	5.30	5.48	5.55	-2.63	-2.40	-2.71	-2.88
X-X	2.19	2.22	2.20	2.19	-1.40	-0.75	-0.58	-0.53
X-C-X	2.09	2.35	2.37	2.38	-1.50	-0.61	-0.41	-0.34
X-V-X	2.86	4.16	4.18	4.17	-6.18	-5.03	-5.41	-5.63
N								
X	3.96	3.97	3.92	3.91				
X-V	5.70	5.90	6.05	6.11	-3.71	-4.30	-4.68	-4.87
X-X	3.67	3.65	3.56	3.53	-4.26	-4.30	-4.29	-4.29
X-C-X	6.64	5.93	6.84	6.81	-1.29	-2.02	-1.01	-1.01
X-V-X	5.02	4.98	4.99	4.99	-8.36	-9.18	-9.66	-9.91
P								
X	6.41	6.66	6.65	6.71				
X-V	4.62	5.04	5.13	5.17	-7.24	-7.85	-8.33	-8.61
X-X	12.02	13.77	13.96	14.12	-0.79	0.44	0.66	0.70
X-C-X	10.76	10.83	10.98	11.02	-2.05	-2.50	-2.32	-2.40
X-V-X	6.93	8.06	8.16	8.18	-11.34	-11.48	-11.94	-12.32
Si								
X	4.38	4.28	4.22	4.21				
X-V	4.04	5.22	5.51	5.64	-5.79	-5.29	-5.51	-5.64
X-X	10.20	11.08	11.06	11.05	1.44	2.51	2.62	2.64
X-C-X	6.59	8.05	8.09	8.11	-2.16	-0.52	-0.36	-0.30
X-V-X	6.52	8.13	8.21	8.22	-7.69	-6.65	-7.04	-7.26
V	5.45	6.22	6.80	7.07				

TABLE I. Defect formation and binding energies (eV/defect) calculated for all systems with cluster defects. Single dopant (X) and non-doped diamond with single vacancy (V) energies are added for comparison.

tures, conducting these extensive simulations falls outside the scope of this study. Additional insight could also be obtained by scanning a broad range of defect configurations to identify the most probable structures under specific conditions. Such investigations often employ high-throughput approaches, Monte Carlo simulations, evolutionary algorithms, machine learning models, or other techniques [71–74]. We point out that we calculate formation energies for supercells with optimised volume; this is because we believe that constant volume calculations are not relevant for our study. Constant volume calculations are commonly used when the formation energy is reported in the *dilute limit*, i.e. at concentrations where no interactions between the defects exist. They are preferred in such cases because fixing the volume helps to more easily account for the so-called supercell error

due to the elastic interactions between periodic images [75]. However, in our work, we report formation energies for each defect at every considered concentration without any extrapolation to the dilute limit. In fact, imposing a fixed volume would introduce unphysical strain and artificially inflate the formation energies, especially for systems representing high defect concentrations. On the other hand, for low concentrations the changes of volumes are minimal. Moreover, our reported values clearly show that the formation energies tend to an asymptotic value as the concentration decreases. As a result, we can reasonably assume that the formation energies reported for a 0.4 % concentration are close to those in the dilute limit.

The formation energy [69, 75–77] of a defect D is computed as:

$$E^f[D] = E_{\text{tot}}[D] - E_{\text{tot}}[\text{bulk}] - \sum_i n_i \mu_i \quad (1)$$

where $E_{\text{tot}}[D]$ and $E_{\text{tot}}[\text{bulk}]$ denote the total energy of the defected structure and the total energy of the equivalent pristine diamond supercell, respectively, n_i is the number of atoms of type i removed ($n_i < 0$, carbon) or added ($n_i > 0$, dopants) into the structure, while μ_i values represent the corresponding chemical potentials, all obtained with the same simulation parameters. The references used for chemical potentials are as follows: *a*) pure diamond (μ_C), *b*) face-centered cubic aluminium (μ_{Al}), *c*) α -rhombohedral boron (μ_B), *d*) molecular nitrogen N_2 (μ_N), *e*) black phosphorus (μ_P), and *f*) diamond lattice of silicon (μ_{Si}). We report the calculated formation energies in Table I. We observe relatively high formation energies in the cases where two large dopants (Al, P, Si) are close to each other without the presence of a vacancy (X-X and X-C-X systems). This is expected, as replacing two carbon atoms with large dopants significantly alters the bond lengths and induce local strain around the defect. Moreover, even single substitutional Al and P dopants yield formation energies between 5.8 - 6.7 eV, while both defects are often used in experiments [17, 19]. We recall that diamond was successfully synthesised with uniformly distributed impurities as large as Mo or W [25], which are significantly larger than the dopants considered in our study. In the case of the cluster defects, it is valuable to calculate the binding energy E^b [75] of the cluster defect D , as it provides insight into whether defects prefer to remain isolated ($E^b > 0$) or combine to form cluster defects ($E^b < 0$). The binding energy is defined as follows:

$$E^b[D] = E^f[D] - nE^f[X] - mE^f[V] \quad (2)$$

where n and m denote the number of dopants (1 or 2) and vacancies (0 or 1) in the defect, respectively, while $E^f[X]$ and $E^f[V]$ are the formation energies of a corresponding single substitutional dopant and a vacancy in the equivalent supercells, respectively.

We observe that the cluster formation energies are generally the lowest in the case of the highest defect

concentration. We ascribe this to the interactions between the defects, as at high concentrations the cluster defects are in close proximity, which leads to binding interactions. This aligns with experimental observations showing that defect clustering predominantly occurs at high dopant concentrations [42, 43]. In the case of small dopant atoms (B, N), X-V-X defects exhibit lower formation and binding energies than X-V defects, consistently with the experimentally observed tendency of N atoms to cluster around vacancies [40]. For large dopant atoms (Al, P, Si), X-V represents the most preferred configuration; in fact, the formation energy of X-V is, in general, even lower than that of X [78]. Moreover, for B and N the X-X configuration is preferred over X-C-X while, for larger dopants, the X-C-X configuration is favoured, except when X=Al. This exception is probably caused by the atypical geometry of Al-X-X systems (section III C). The binding energy is negative in nearly all cases with the exception of P and Si in X-X configuration; this suggests that the formation of these impurities may not be preferred. These findings are consistent with what has been reported in the literature [42, 48, 49, 79].

A. Methodology and general features

a. Geometry analysis The first step in our analysis is to investigate the influence of the defect on the geometry of the pristine structure. As expected, the introduction of a cluster defect reduces the number of symmetries compared to the pristine structure (space group $Fd\bar{3}m$, group number 227), and to the case of a single dopant coordinating a regular tetrahedron (point group T_d , Figure 3a) of carbon atoms ($F43m$, #216) [56]; we will here refer to the latter systems as “X” models. The only X structures with the lowest number of symmetries are those doped with nitrogen. In such geometries, the nitrogen atom is much closer to three carbon atoms than to the fourth, thus forming a trigonal pyramidal configuration (C_{3v} Figure 3b). Such systems own the symmetries of the trigonal space group $R3m$ (#160). We observed that the environment of the same dopant is characterised by the same point group (T_d or C_{3v}) irrespective of the concentration. The point group does not change even for the structures doped by the cluster defects. The only exception is the N-3-X-C-X system as we will see in the following discussion.

b. Electronic structure analysis We then proceed with the analysis of the electronic structure. As a first step, we need to establish a method for measuring the width of the band gap about the Fermi level. Usually, the band gap is measured as the energy difference between the conduction band minimum and the valence band maximum; however, when numerous highly localised intermediate bands are present, the situation is much less straightforward. Adding defects to the structure can result in the creation of localised bands located below or above the Fermi level; the latter bands, when populated,

FIG. 3. Schematic representing all coordination polyhedra found in the studied systems: (a) regular tetrahedron (T_d), (b) trigonal pyramidal configuration (C_{3v}), (c) distorted octahedron (D_{3d}), (d) distorted trigonal prismatic configuration (C_{3v}), (e) irregular tetrahedron (C_s) and (f) irregular pyramidal configuration (C_s).

represent trapped electrons which do not contribute to the n -type conductivity. To identify such bands, we calculate the *generalised inverse participation ratio* (IPR) [80] by utilising the projected density of states via:

$$IPR(\epsilon) = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^N g(A_i, \epsilon)^2}{(\sum_{i=1}^N g(A_i, \epsilon))^2} \quad (3)$$

where $g(A_i, \epsilon)$ represents the density of states projected on the A_i atom-centred hydrogen-like orbitals and N is the number of atoms in the cell. In the forthcoming analysis, with the term *valence band* we refer to the occupied bands of the host matrix in the ground state, while with the term *impurity bands* we refer to the bands appearing due to the presence of the dopant. We will focus on the band gap which corresponds to the final electron jump to the conductive (delocalised) states in the conduction band, thus resulting in nonmetal-to-metal transition by means of n -type conductivity. Nevertheless, we recognise that the electron transition from the valence band to any localised band above the Fermi level results in the p -type conductivity, but this is not the focus of the present work [81]. Therefore, we measure the size of the band gap as the energy difference between the bottom of the conduction band and the localised intermediate band with the highest energy that lies below it ($\Delta = \epsilon_{CBM} - \epsilon_{IB_{max}}$), as indicated in Figure 4a. According to this definition, the band gap size is null in the case of the n -type degenerate semiconductors, as the Fermi level is located in the conduction band; thus, these materials show n -type metallic properties. To parameterise this situation consistently with our previous work [56], we use the definition of the generalised band gap. In the case of n -type degenerate semiconductors, we measure band gap as an energy difference between the bottom of the conduction band and the Fermi level ($\Delta = \epsilon_{CBM} - \epsilon_F$) as shown in Figure 4b. As a result, negative values then represent the

FIG. 4. Schematic demonstrating the method of measuring the band gap width in this work. The electronic band structure of the (a) N-4-X-V-X system represents the vast majority of considered systems; the band gap is measured as a difference between the conduction band minimum (ϵ_{CBM}) and the intermediate localised band with the highest energy ($\epsilon_{IB_{max}}$). The band dispersion of the (b) P-2-X-X indicates the method of measurement for degenerate *n-type* systems where the band gap is measured as the energy difference between the ϵ_{CBM} and the Fermi level (ϵ_F) and is of negative value. The Fermi level is set to 0 eV.

depth of the Fermi level in the conduction band. Due to this definition, we can analyse trends consistently with structures realising positive band gaps. For the clarity of the analysis, with the term *energy gap* we refer to any region where no electron energy is allowed, while with *band gap* we mean the energy gap located below the bottom of the conduction band according to definition mentioned above.

The electronic band structures are computed along the standard [82] piece-wise linear path joining the high-symmetry points in the irreducible Brillouin zone of the face-centred cubic lattice, regardless of the space group of the considered structure; we make this choice to facilitate the interested reader in the comparison with the previously studied diamond-doped systems with no cluster defects [56] where most of the considered systems realised this kind of lattice. In the majority of the cases, we observe that the band gap size decreases with the decrease in concentration, while a few exceptions can be found in the case of X-V-X and X-C-X structures (see section “Generalised band gap as a function of the defect concentration” in Supplemental Material [83]). Such a deviation from the trend is caused either by a separation of the impurity band from the conduction band (B-, Si-X-V-X systems), thus forming a new intermediate band, or by a change of geometry (N-3-X-C-X, see section III D). Moreover, as expected, all doped systems show a narrower band gap than pristine diamond struc-

tures.

c. General features of the electronic structure In general, we observe that every defect type forms a degenerate semiconductor at least in the case of one dopant atomic type, mostly at higher concentrations. Furthermore, when we increase the concentration we decrease the resemblance between the band structures of the cluster defect systems and X-doped systems with the same defect concentration. This is especially true for the X-X and X-C-X defects as well as for X-V structures doped by large dopants, whose band structures resemble the X systems the most. In many cases, the band structure of the systems doped in the highest concentration (6.25 %) of the defect does not resemble the band structure of the lower concentrations (1.85, 0.78 and 0.4 %); this is expected, as the distance between the defects in the former case is short enough and defects cannot be considered as isolated. We observe that the evolution of the band structure with gradually decreasing concentration can be summarised as a following path: *a)* Degenerate semiconductor of *p-type*; *b)* The Fermi level moves towards the valence band maximum; *c)* The Fermi level is in the valence band near the valence band maximum; *d)* Split of the band(s) formed by dopant states from the valence band. The process is similar in the case of *n-type* semiconductor; the only difference is that the Fermi level moves to the bottom of the conduction band and the separation is from the conduction band. If the system is a degenerate semiconductor and no energy gap exists in the band structure at high concentration, we can distinguish whether the semiconductor will follow the path of *p-* or *n-type* semiconductor presented above by analysing the curvature of the bands which are crossed by the Fermi level. If we observe a negative (concave) curvature of these bands at Γ , the semiconductor will follow the *p-type* path when the concentration is decreased.

We continue our analysis by considering the projected density of states (PDOS). The first thing we notice is that irrespective of the type of dopant, concentration or defect type, the p_x and p_y orbitals centred at each atomic site are degenerate. The states around the Fermi level are added to the pristine band structure mostly by dopants and their first neighbours, which suggests hybridisation of their orbitals. After a defect is created, additional states are added to the top of the valence band, the bottom of the conduction band, or into the former band gap, thus creating separated localised bands or any combinations of these options. The dopant atomic type and the kind of defect determine the position of the dopant states in a non-trivial way; however, we can identify some general trends. When X-V structures are doped by dopants with large atomic radii (Al, P, Si), the top of the valence band and the bottom of the conduction bands show a *d-* and *s-*orbital-like character, respectively (Figure 5a). We ascribe this behaviour to the octahedral configuration of the dopant with its neighbours: as four carbon neighbours lie on a plane containing a dopant, the *d-* orbitals represent the best approximation of the electron

FIG. 5. Projected density of states (PDOS) of (a) P-3-X-V, (b) Al-3-X-C-X and (c) B-4-X-V-X systems. The “X”, “neig”, “brid C” and “far C” labels correspond to the projections onto the dopant atoms, the dopant neighbours, the bridging carbon between dopants in the X-C-X structure and carbon far from the defect, respectively. The “s”, “p” and “d” labels in plot (a) represent s , p , d orbitals centred at the dopant atomic site. The *Inverse participation ratio* value (“IPR”) is equal to one for completely delocalised states, while for maximally localised states the IPR equals the number of atoms in the unit cell (127). The values of dopants and neighbours are normalised according to their number in the system.

density at the dopant site. By analysing the PDOSs of the X-C-X systems, we observe that the bridging carbon located between the two dopants acts more as a different type of dopant than as the other dopant’s neighbours or dopants themselves. In fact, together with the dopants, it contributes to the majority of the states around the Fermi level; in degenerate p-type semiconductors, the energy levels above the Fermi level but still in the valence band are almost solely formed by the states of this carbon (Figure 5b). Therefore, we can conclude that the bridging carbon in X-C-X systems has a major role in forming degenerate semiconductors. The other notable PDOSs correspond to the X-V-X systems. As we will see, the X-V-X structures feature many highly localised intermediate states. Therefore, these states are nearly solely contributed by the dopant atoms; to stress this, we report the PDOS of the B-4-X-V-X system together with the corresponding IPR in Figure 5c as an example.

d. How to engineer width and character of the band gap We here recall that we measure the size of the band

gap as the minimum energy needed to achieve n -type conductivity. In our previous research [56], we observed the dependence of the size of the band gap on the X-C interatomic distance, as it determines the degree of orbital hybridisation between the dopant and the surrounding carbon atoms. Here, we shall see that such a clear relation no longer exists; however, atomic radii and X-C distances still affect the local distributions of the electronic density in various ways. We then proceed by analysing each defect type separately in the following way: We start by considering more general descriptors such as Hirshfeld atom charges [84] and bond covalencies [85], the latter defined in terms of atom-projected density of states; subsequently, to dive even into more details, we analyse the local distribution of the electronic density by means of the orbital polarisation descriptor [86–89]. Orbital polarisation $\mathcal{P}_{i,j}(A, B)$ is defined as:

$$\mathcal{P}'_{i,j}(A, B) = \frac{n_i(A) - n_j(B)}{n_i(A) + n_j(B)} \quad (4)$$

where $n_i(A)$ and $n_j(B)$ are the occupancies of the i and j set of atomic orbitals centered on the atom A and B , respectively. Thanks to this definition, the $\mathcal{P}'_{i,j}(A, B)$ is an effective and convenient way to measure the excess of charge in the i orbital relative to the j orbital. To simplify the notation, we will use the symbol $\mathcal{P}'_{i,j}(A)$ when comparing the charge in the orbitals of the same atom ($A = B$). We adopt atom-centred hydrogen-like wavefunctions to calculate the orbital polarisations at the site of the substituents and the neighbouring carbon atoms. With this approach, we partition the electronic density according to the spatial character of the orbital and examine the possible preferential charge distributions in the local environment of the dopant. Since p_x and p_y orbitals are degenerate, it is enough to consider $\mathcal{P}_{p_x, p_z}(X)$ ($= \mathcal{P}_{p_y, p_z}(X)$) and $\mathcal{P}_{p_x, p_z}(C)$ ($= \mathcal{P}_{p_y, p_z}(C)$) in our analysis as $\mathcal{P}_{p_x, p_y}(X) = \mathcal{P}_{p_x, p_y}(C) = 0$.

Finally, we compare the relative occupation of the p_x ($= p_y$) and p_z orbital of the dopant and the surrounding carbon atoms. In this way, we obtain details about the spatial distribution of the charge along the bond axis. As it would be too dispersive to treat each carbon neighbour and dopant separately, we will rely on the average values of the descriptors for neighbours and dopants, unless specified otherwise. The average orbital polarisation $\mathcal{P}_{i,j}(A, B)$ is calculated as follows:

$$\mathcal{P}_{i,j}(A, B) = \frac{\sum_{p=1}^{s_A} n_i(A_p)/s_A - \sum_{p=1}^{s_B} n_j(B_p)/s_B}{\sum_{p=1}^{s_A} n_i(A_p)/s_A + \sum_{p=1}^{s_B} n_j(B_p)/s_B} \quad (5)$$

where s_A and s_B are the numbers of atoms of A (in our case dopants) and B (neighbours) kinds, respectively. The average values of the covalency $C_{X,C}$, Hirshfeld charges $\mathcal{H}(A)$ and polarisations of the same atoms

($\mathcal{P}_{i,j}(A)$) are calculated as arithmetic means:

$$\mathcal{P}_{i,j}(A) = \frac{1}{s_A} \sum_{p=1}^{s_A} \mathcal{P}'_{i,j}(A_p) \quad (6)$$

$$C_{X,C} = \frac{1}{s_A} \left(\sum_{p=1}^{s_{A_1}} C'_{X_1,C_p} + \sum_{p=1}^{s_{A_2}} C'_{X_2,C_p} \right) \quad (7)$$

$$\mathcal{H}(A) = \frac{1}{s_A} \sum_{p=1}^{s_A} \mathcal{H}'(A_p) \quad (8)$$

where s_A is the number of atoms A (neighbours or dopants), the X-C bond covalency ($C_{X,C}$) is calculated between each dopant (X_1 or X_2) and all their respective neighbours (s_{A_1} , s_{A_2}) separately and then averaged by the number of all neighbours (s_A). The $\mathcal{P}'_{i,j}(A)$ and $\mathcal{H}'(A)$ always correspond to the orbital polarisations considering the i and j orbital and the Hirshfeld charge on the single atom A , respectively, while the $C'_{X,C}$ represents the covalency of the single bond between two atoms X and C .

B. X-V defect

a. Geometry analysis Structures with an X-V defect (Figure 1a) can be split into two groups according to the local environment of the dopant: structures doped by atomic types with large atomic radii (Al, Si, P) and small radii (B, N). During the relaxation procedure, dopants with large radii migrate from the initial position in such a way that they eventually create distorted octahedra formed by six neighbouring carbon atoms (D_{3d} , Figure 3c), effectively suppressing the vacancy from the structure. This configuration is often called *split-vacancy* configuration and is commonly formed in the case of impurities with large atomic radii [28, 90]. The regular octahedral environment allows to realise the symmetries of the trigonal space group $R\bar{3}m$ (#166). Systems with small radii dopants preserve the existence of the vacancy next to the dopant, thus creating a trigonal pyramidal configuration (C_{3v} , Figure 3b). These systems realise a trigonal space group but with a reduced number of symmetries compared to the previous case ($R\bar{3}m$, #160). Interestingly, we observe that the increase in the multiplicity of the cell, i.e. decreasing the defect concentration, decreases the X-C distances at fixed dopant atomic type (Figure 6).

b. Electronic structure analysis We begin by considering X-V models doped by large dopant atoms (Al, Si, P); we recall that dopants in these structures coordinate carbon octahedra (Figure 3c). At all concentrations, we observe that all the systems display behaviour as in *p-type* doping, despite P and N being electron donors (see Figure 8c-d); an exception is found for the B-, P-2-X-V models, which do not have any band gap. On the other hand, band structures of the systems doped by Al and Si show resemblance to the X structures doped by the

FIG. 6. Interatomic distance between the dopant atom and the carbon neighbours in its first coordination shell as a function of the dopant concentration.

FIG. 7. Electronic band structures of (a) Si-3-X-V and (b) Si-3-X system, the red arrow connects k-points corresponding to the minimal-energy transition to the conduction band. The Fermi level is set to 0 eV.

same dopant but with a narrower band gap (Figure 7). The band structures of the second group, doped by B and N which preserve the presence of the vacancy (Figure 3b), are similar to the band structure of a diamond which contains sole vacancy. As shown in Figure 8a-c), the presence of a vacancy induces the formation of intermediate band(s) (IBs) in the band gap of the pristine diamond. The most significant difference between the B-X-V (Figure 8b) and N-X-V (Figure 8c) is the position of one of the impurity bands; in the B-doped case, this band is above the Fermi level, while in the N-doped case, it is below the Fermi level. The same holds for all considered concentrations. The positions of the calculated intermediate bands are comparable with those reported in the literature (e.g. Al-X-V [91], B-X-V [44], N-X-V [64, 92]).

c. Charged states To evaluate the influence of charge states on the positions of the impurity bands within the band gap, we perform a study of charged X-V defects in 1.85 % concentration. The considered charges span from completely empty to completely filled impurity

FIG. 8. Electronic band structures of (a) V-3-X, (b) B-3-X-V, (c) N-3-X-V and (d) P-3-X-V systems, the red arrow connects k-points corresponding to the minimal-energy transition to the conduction band. The Fermi level is set to 0 eV.

bands closest to the Fermi level within the band gap. For instance, the N-X-V defect introduces two closely packed bands in the middle of the band gap, which together can accommodate up to four electrons. In the neutral state, these bands are occupied by a single electron, thus, we consider charge states of +1, 0, -1, -2 and -3. The charge states and assigned spin states are consistent with computational and experimental studies on various X-V defects (Al [91], B [69], N [40], P [93], Si [30]), although many studies do not consider highly charged states such as -3. Such high charge states are unlikely to form; nevertheless, they are useful for observing trends in the change of positions of impurity bands.

In all five cases, removal of electrons from the defect shifts impurity bands towards lower energies, while adding electrons shifts the bands to higher energies. The only exception is positively charged silicon, where the band gap changes are negligible. However, this trend is not always apparent from the Table II due to the method of our band gap measurement. Negatively charged B-X-V defects have the uppermost band already merged with

the CBM, leading to a sudden increase in the band gap size. This happens because now the band gap is measured as an energy difference between the CBM and the top of the second intermediate band, closer to the valence band (see Figure 8b). Similarly, P-X-V seemingly even exhibits an opposite trend; this is due to the fact that one of the impurity bands is merged with the CBM in neutral state, as this band moves towards lower energies, the band gap narrows (see Figure 8d). This band fully detaches from the CBM once the charge is higher than +1, which results in a significant drop in the band gap width. With these considerations, the changes in impurity band energies with respect to changes in charge states are evident. The intended formation of the charged defects can then serve as one of the techniques to tune the band gap size and positions of the impurity bands.

Charge	Al	B	N	P	Si
0 ($S = 0$)	2.53	0.35	1.89	1.91	2.84
3				0.20	
				D 0	
2				0.14	2.66
				D $1/2$	0
1	2.67	0.60	2.32	1.69	2.69
	0	0	0	1	$1/2$
0	2.42	0.32	1.60	1.85	2.71
	$1/2$	$1/2$	$1/2$	$1/2$	1
-1	2.11	0.86	0.73	2.08	2.59
	1	M 1	1	0	$1/2$
-2	1.94	0.67	0.48		2.42
	$1/2$	M $1/2$	$1/2$		0
-3	1.75	0.47	0.25		
	0	M 0	0		

TABLE II. Generalised band gap values (eV) of X-V defects at 1.85 % concentration in different charge states. Spin state of each defect is reported in the second row below the band gap size. The labels “D” and “M” denote cases where one of the intermediate bands has detached from or merged with the conduction band, leading to abrupt changes in the band gap size. The first row corresponds to the neutral defects without spin polarisation, as considered in our analysis.

d. How to engineer width of the band gap We begin our analysis of the X-V systems by considering how the concentration of the defect affects the band gap size. In the case of all cluster defects, we observe that the interval which characterises the spread of the band gap values for the same dopant atoms with the change of concentration is significantly larger than in the case of structures doped by single dopant (X). This is because the drop of the band gap size between 1.85 % and 6.25 % concentration is enormous (up to 2 eV) in the case of cluster defects. At such a high defect concentration, wide impurity bands fill nearly the whole pristine band gap, thus reducing its size, or even closing the gap completely. Due to this reason, we believe it is more descriptive to report the

FIG. 9. Generalised band gap as a function of Hirshfeld charges of the dopant first neighbours (a) and dopant (b) in the X-V systems.

spread of the band gap values for the same atom with 6.25 % concentration neglected. In the X-V systems, the spread of the energy values is no more than 0.6 eV with one exception being phosphorus, when we consider only lower concentrations than 6.25 %. This value is very similar to the X systems.

We continue by examining the Hirshfeld charges of the dopant and neighbouring atoms (Figure 9). The Hirshfeld charges of the large dopant atoms (Al, P, Si) and their neighbours depend on the atomic radius of the dopant; the value of the charge increases at decreasing radius. Moreover, systems with narrower band gaps (B, N) exhibit the largest absolute values of the Hirshfeld charges of the neighbours (Figure 9a) and the smallest for the dopant (Figure 9b). We remind that smaller dopants preserve the vacancy while larger atoms form an octahedral configuration. Therefore, it seems that there is a connection between the values of the Hirshfeld charge and the coordination environment of the dopant. Similarly, the dopant-neighbour bond covalencies $C_{X,C}$ depend on the atomic radii of the larger dopant atoms but we do not observe any visible general trend for the band gap size as a function of the covalency (Figure 10). However, when we compare dopants with the same local environments (D_{3d} or C_{3v}), we can see that the band gap size tends to increase with larger covalency values. Moreover, we recognise that the covalency value increases with decreasing concentration; the opposite trend has been found for the structures with X defect [56]. This can be ascribed to the fact that the X-C distances in the X-V systems decrease with decreasing concentration while the opposite is true for X systems, thus determining the degree of orbital hybridisation and therefore the bond covalency. Furthermore, the *n-type* doped systems show the largest covalency values, consistently with the X models. This

FIG. 10. Generalised band gap as a function of the X-C bond covalency $C_{X,C}$ in the X-V systems.

shows us that even when the *n-type* dopants create *p-type* structures when clustered with vacancy, they still preserve more covalent bonds with carbon neighbours than *p-type* dopants. Nevertheless, we observe that the covalency values are lower for every dopant when compared to X structures.

As expected, structures that preserve the existence of the vacancy (trigonal pyramidal configuration, Figure 3b) display higher absolute $\mathcal{P}_{p_x,p_z}(C)$ and $\mathcal{P}_{p_x,p_z}(X)$ values due to the distorted environment around dopant (Figure 11). This is especially visible for $\mathcal{P}_{p_x,p_z}(X)$, where structures with octahedral configuration show values lower by one order of magnitude. Moreover, the $\mathcal{P}_{p_x,p_z}(X)$ values depend on the radius of the large atoms, while they do not change significantly with the change of concentration. Since the large absolute $\mathcal{P}_{p_x,p_z}(X)$ values mean smaller band gap size, the narrow band gaps can be achieved by doping with the dopant which forms trigonal pyramidal configuration, i.e. dopants with small radii (B, N). B-doped structures display a narrower band gap and positive values of $\mathcal{P}_{p_x,p_z}(X)$ while N-doped systems show a wider band gap and negative $\mathcal{P}_{p_x,p_z}(X)$. Therefore, it seems that the number of valence electrons is crucial in determining the size of the band gap in the case of small dopants even when all dopants create *p-type* diamonds. Finally, we do not observe any regular trend of the band gap size as a function of $\mathcal{P}_{p_z,p_z}(X,C)$ (Figure 12), while $\mathcal{P}_{p_x,p_x}(X,C)$ values closer to zero correspond to structures with trigonal pyramidal configuration and, therefore, smaller band gap.

In summary, dopants with small atomic radii realise significantly narrower band gaps while showing larger dopant polarisations $\mathcal{P}_{p_x,p_z}(X)$ by one order of magnitude. When considering *p-type* dopants, we can order the dopant coordination numbers (CN) with respect to the size of the band gap from the largest to smallest as follows: tetrahedral (CN = 4, Figure 3a) octahedral (CN = 6, Figure 3c) trigonal pyramidal (CN = 3, Figure 3b) dopant coordinations. Moreover, in the case of octahedral coordination, the values of $C_{X,C}$, $\mathcal{P}_{p_x,p_z}(X)$, $\mathcal{P}_{p_x,p_x}(X,C)$, $\mathcal{P}_{p_z,p_z}(X,C)$ as well as Hirshfeld charges of the dopant and its neighbouring atoms depend on the atomic radii of the dopants. In the case of smaller atoms,

FIG. 11. Generalised band gap as a function of (a) $\mathcal{P}_{p_x, p_z}(C)$ and (b) $\mathcal{P}_{p_x, p_z}(X)$ in the X-V systems.

FIG. 12. Generalised band gap as a function of (a) $\mathcal{P}_{p_x, p_x}(X, C)$ and (b) $\mathcal{P}_{p_z, p_z}(X, C)$ in the X-V systems.

the number of electrons (electron acceptor vs. donor) seems to have a more important role in affecting the values of such physical descriptors.

C. X-X defect

a. Geometry analysis In the structures with an X-X type of defect (Figure 1b), each dopant coordinates three carbon atoms in a trigonal pyramidal coordination environment (C_{3v} , Figure 3b). In general, the geometric environments of each of the two X dopants are very similar; the only exceptions are represented by the structures doped with aluminium, where one of the dopants has six

carbon neighbours (Figure 3d) and the X-X distance is as large as ~ 2.2 Å. We observe that in all the cases the X-C distances are smaller than the X-X distances. This is especially significant in the case of dopants with small atomic radii, where the difference between X-C distances and X-X distance is ~ 0.4 Å for boron and ~ 0.7 Å for nitrogen. The structures realise the symmetries of the trigonal space groups $R\bar{3}m$ (#166) or $R3m$ (#160), according to whether the local environments of both dopants are identical or not, respectively.

b. Electronic structure analysis X-X systems doped with Al, P or Si (large atomic radii) show band structures which resemble those of the X models the most (see section “Electronic band structures at 1.85 % concentration” in Supplemental Material [83]). The structures doped by P are degenerate *n-type* semiconductors as the corresponding X-doped structure, while systems doped by Al and Si display a narrower band gap when compared to their X-doped equivalents. However, even if Al-X-X and Al-X band structures are very similar, the major difference is in the electron occupation of the impurity bands. The Al-X-X systems exhibit a fully occupied impurity band near the valence band, thus it cannot contribute to the *p-type* conductivity and the systems behave as an *intrinsic (i-type)* semiconductors. Similarly, systems doped by N show *i-type* behaviour, as N atoms contribute with very deep fully occupied donor states closer to the valence band than to the conduction band, consistently with other studies [94]. Moreover, B-doped systems are either a degenerate *p-type* semiconductor or form an empty acceptor IB 0.7 eV above the Fermi level at the lowest concentration of the defect. This is a well known feature when the clustering of boron atoms in diamond reduces the conductivity [42].

c. How to engineer width of the band gap We recall that in the following discussion, we will use the generalised band gap to measure band gap size in the case of the *n-type* degenerate semiconductors (section III A). The generalised band gap is measured as an energy difference between the bottom of the conduction band and the Fermi level ($\Delta = \epsilon_{CBM} - \epsilon_F$). As a result, negative values represent the depth of the Fermi level in the conduction band. In X-X systems, both dopants are in very similar or equal coordination environments, resulting in nearly equal values of descriptors such as X-C bond covalency and polarisations. The only exceptions are Al-doped systems, where one of the dopants is close to six carbon atoms instead of three (Figure 3d), while the second dopant is in an expected trigonal pyramidal environment (Figure 3b) similar to the other X-X structures. Moreover, the band structures and density of states of all X-X defects are the most similar to the structures with just one dopant. The spread of the band gap sizes with fixed atomic types for different concentrations varies noticeably more than it is for X systems. The width of this interval is 1.1 eV when we neglect 6.25 % concentration. We observe that the highest absolute (positive and negative) values of the dopant Hirshfeld charges cor-

FIG. 13. Generalised band gap as a function of Hirshfeld charges of the dopant's first neighbours (a) and of the dopant (b) in the X-X systems.

FIG. 14. Generalised band gap as a function of the X-C bond covalency $C_{X,C}$ in the X-X systems.

respond to the *n-type* dopants (Figure 13b). Furthermore, it seems that the increase in the neighbours' Hirshfeld charges (Figure 13a) decreases the band gap size of the systems with positive band gaps (all systems except P-doped). A very similar trend can be found when we inspect the plot of dopant-carbon bond covalency $C_{X,C}$ (Figure 14). Increasing the $C_{X,C}$ decreases positive band gap width, while Al-doped systems are very slightly off the trend. However, we need to take into account the fact that Al-doped systems are the only ones with non-regular geometry; in fact, the presented covalency value is an average of very high (dopant with six neighbours) and relatively low (dopant with three neighbours) covalency values. Even in the case of X-X structures, we can distinguish a covalency threshold which acts as a boundary between *p-type* and *n-type* doped structures. Moreover, if we neglect Al-2-X-C-X, the difference between *p-* and *n-type* covalencies is of significant size (0.6 eV).

We proceed by considering orbital polarizations of the dopant $\mathcal{P}_{p_x, p_z}(X)$ and surrounding carbons $\mathcal{P}_{p_x, p_z}(C)$ as shown in Figure 15. In both cases, an increase in the po-

FIG. 15. Generalised band gap as a function of (a) $\mathcal{P}_{p_x, p_x}(X, C)$ and (b) $\mathcal{P}_{p_z, p_z}(X, C)$ in the X-X systems.

FIG. 16. Generalised band gap as a function of (a) $\mathcal{P}_{p_x, p_x}(X, C)$ and (b) $\mathcal{P}_{p_z, p_z}(X, C)$ in the X-X systems.

larisation seems to decrease the size of the band gap when *p-type* systems and Si are considered. Secondly, *n-type* dopants show $\mathcal{P}_{p_x, p_z}(C)$ values close to zero and only negative $\mathcal{P}_{p_x, p_z}(X)$. The *n-type* dopants exhibit the highest $\mathcal{P}_{p_x, p_x}(X, C)$ and $\mathcal{P}_{p_z, p_z}(X, C)$ values, while they are the only cases realising positive $\mathcal{P}_{p_z, p_z}(X, C)$ (Figure 16). On the other hand, we do not see any regular trend with the increase of charge at the atomic dopant side of the bond (increase of $\mathcal{P}_{p_x, p_x}(X, C)$ and $\mathcal{P}_{p_z, p_z}(X, C)$) as the band gap width of the B-doped structures is reduced more significantly by introducing the second dopant.

In summary, by realising an X-X clustering defect, we can still create *p-* and *n-type* structures by doping with *p-* and *n-type* dopants. We noticed that adding the second

dopant reduces the band gap size of *p-type* and Si-doped structures when compared to the single dopant case; adding the second phosphorus preserves the *n-type* degenerate properties while keeping the depth of the Fermi level in the conduction band nearly unchanged. On the other hand, donor states in the nitrogen-doped systems are now much deeper, that is, much closer to the valence band than to the conduction band. Moreover, we saw that the increase in $\mathcal{P}_{p_x, p_z}(X)$, $\mathcal{P}_{p_x, p_z}(C)$ or $C_{X,C}$ decreases the band gap width of the *p-type* and Si systems.

D. X-C-X defect

a. Geometry analysis Regarding the X-C-X defect type (Figure 1c), the number of symmetries depends on the similarity of the local environments of both dopants: when X-C distances about one dopant are the same as about the other dopant, the number of symmetries owned by the structure is higher than in the case of dissimilar distances set. In general, this is true for all the kinds of defects that contain two dopants. The local environments of the two dopants in the X-C-X systems are very similar irrespective of the dopant atomic type and form irregular tetrahedrons with their neighbours (C_s , Figure 3e), except for nitrogen doping. In this case, one of the nitrogen atoms is much closer to three out of four surrounding carbons, thus forming a trigonal pyramidal coordination environment (C_{3v} , Figure 3b), similarly to what was observed in N-doped diamond structures with no clustering defect [56]; the local environment of the second dopant forms an irregular tetrahedron with its neighbours (C_s , Figure 3e). However, in the N-3-X-C-X system, both nitrogen atoms have the same local C_{3v} environment. In the case of a few 16-atom models, the geometry of the cluster defect was such that the effective primitive cell could be built by considering an 8-atom unit; this occurs for the B-, P- and Si-doped structures which have the symmetries of the orthorhombic space group $Am\bar{m}2$ (#38), while Al- and N-doped systems require 16-atoms supercells with the orthorhombic crystal symmetries of the space group $Imm2$ (#44). 54, 128 and 250-atom systems realise symmetries with either monoclinic Cm (#8) or orthorhombic $Imm2$ (#44) symmetry, depending on the local environments of the two dopant atoms as mentioned at the beginning of the paragraph. In general, structures doped by B, P and Si are of higher symmetry than those doped by Al and N.

b. Electronic structure analysis The X-C-X systems doped by Al and B are of *p-type* with only one energy gap, as is expected in X-doped cases (see section “Electronic band structures at 1.85 % concentration” in Supplemental Material [83]). The structures doped by isovalent Si exhibit behaviour similar to *intrinsic* semiconductors with one narrower band gap when compared to Si-doped X-case; the only exception is the Si-5-X-C-X system realising two energy gaps, due to the presence of the intermediate band in the middle of the former band gap

FIG. 17. Electronic band structures of (a) N-4-X-C-X and (b) N-4-X-V systems, the red arrow connects k-points corresponding to the minimal-energy transition to the conduction band. The Fermi level is set to 0 eV.

(Figure 27b). Moreover, B-doped structures are forming degenerate *p-type* semiconductors, as the Fermi level is crossing their valence bands even in the case of the lowest concentration. Systems doped by N in high concentrations (6.25, 1.85 %) exhibit *intrinsic-like* properties; this can be ascribed to the proximity of the defect to its replicas in neighbouring cells. Structures doped with N in low concentrations (0.78, 0.4 %) and all doped with P form an occupied intermediate band below the conduction band minimum, which is typical for *n-type* semiconductors [81]; the position of the P donor band is consistent with other reported investigations [48]. We observe that X-C-X structures doped with N in low concentrations are very similar to X-structures, as the impurity level is located at nearly identical depth below the conduction band (Figure 17). In the case of phosphorus, the X structure is a degenerate *n-type* semiconductor in all concentrations, while X-C-X already forms an intermediate donor band below the conduction band minimum at 1.85 %. Therefore, in the case of P, we can assume that to obtain the impurity level at a certain depth, it is enough to use a much lower concentration of X-type defect than of the X-C-X defect.

c. How to engineer width of the band gap As mentioned in the previous paragraphs, X-C-X systems contain two main anomalies: *i*) N-3-X-C-X has a relaxed geometry which differs from other concentrations, resulting in an insulating structure; and *ii*) the size of the band gap of Si-5-X-C-X drops when compared to Si-3-X-C-X and Si-4-X-C-X as a result of a new intermediate band introduced into the energy gap. Due to this reason, the range of the band gap sizes can vary as much as more than 2 eV even when we do not consider 6.25 % concentration. Without these two anomalies, the band gap values range within 1.1 eV. This variation is promi-

FIG. 18. Generalised band gap as a function of Hirshfeld charges of the dopant's first neighbours (a) and of the dopant (b) in the X-C-X systems.

nent in *p-type* and Si-doped structures, while the position of the donor level in the *n-type* structures does not change rapidly with the change of concentration. We do not observe any regular trend of the band gap as a function of Hirshfeld charges of the neighbours and the dopant (Figure 18). However, the change of the Hirshfeld charge with respect to changing concentration is much more significant and irregular when compared to other defect types. Moreover, we observe that dopants with larger atomic radii realise only the positive Hirshfeld charge of the dopant while the dopants with smaller radii show mostly negative values (Figure 18b). We do not observe any clear trend of the band gap as a function of the dopant-neighbour bond covalencies $C_{X,C}$ either (Figure 19). Previously studied X systems [56] showed clear $C_{X,C}$ threshold between *p-type* and *n-type* systems. This threshold is no longer visible due to the significant change of covalency in structures doped with nitrogen; in these cases, the dopant which realises symmetries of the C_{3v} point group (Figure 3b) shows high covalency X-C values, at variance with the reduced covalent character of the bonds of the other dopant. As a result, the average covalency is shifted to considerably lower values when compared to the X case. In fact, the donor band below the conduction band minimum is nearly solely formed by states of nitrogen exhibiting high $C_{X,C}$ values without the contribution of the second dopant. If we considered the covalency values of this dopant only, at 0.9 eV, we would find the threshold mentioned above as well as a threshold where band gap sizes suddenly decrease. The only exception to this rule is the already mentioned N-3-X-C-X anomaly with a wider band gap. Moreover, it seems that in the majority of the cases, the band gap gets narrower for higher covalency values at fixed dopant atomic kind. This is most notable in the case of silicon,

FIG. 19. Generalised band gap as a function of the X-C bond covalency $C_{X,C}$ in X-C-X systems. N* values correspond to the $C_{X,C}$ of the nitrogen which is responsible for the *n-type* character of the structure.

where a sudden rise of covalency in the case of 0.4 % concentration correlates with the decrease in the band gap size.

At first glance, it is apparent that *p-type* dopants show high positive $\mathcal{P}_{p_x,p_z}(X)$ values while being highly concentration-dependent (Figure 20). At constant concentration, Al-doped systems realise a narrower band gap and higher $\mathcal{P}_{p_x,p_z}(X)$ values compared to B-doped systems. Therefore, we might conclude that higher $\mathcal{P}_{p_x,p_z}(X)$ means smaller band gap size when doped by *p-type* dopants. On the other hand, systems doped by silicon, and *n-type* systems realise $|\mathcal{P}_{p_x,p_z}(X)| \approx 0$. In fact, electronic properties of nitrogen-doped systems can be easily distinguished by the $\mathcal{P}_{p_x,p_z}(X)$ values as negative $|\mathcal{P}_{p_x,p_z}(X)| \approx -6\%$ correspond to the *intrinsic-like* N-2-, N-3-X-C-X structures, while $|\mathcal{P}_{p_x,p_z}(X)| \approx 0$ to the *n-type* structures of lower concentrations. However, the nitrogen-doped *n-type* systems, similarly to $C_{X,C}$, suffer from averaging dopants' values, as charge of the first dopant is preferentially distributed along p_x axis while it is along p_z axis for the second dopant; this results in an average $\mathcal{P}_{p_x,p_z}(X)$ value close to zero. We do not find any conclusive results by observing the band gap size as a function of $\mathcal{P}_{p_x,p_z}(C)$. We observe very similar trends of the $\mathcal{P}_{p_x,p_x}(X,C)$ and $\mathcal{P}_{p_z,p_z}(X,C)$ values to these observed in X cases (Figure 21). It seems that the decrease of charge at the *p-type* dopant site ($\mathcal{P}_{p_x,p_x}(X,C)$ and $\mathcal{P}_{p_z,p_z}(X,C)$) of the X-C bond decreases the size of the band gap, while values close to zero and positive values correspond to the *n-type* dopants. The major deviation from the trend corresponds to the previously mentioned Si-5-X-C-X system.

As we observed, the systems with higher positive $\mathcal{P}_{p_x,p_z}(X)$ values correspond to the *p-type* semiconductors, while low absolute $\mathcal{P}_{p_x,p_z}(X)$ values correspond to the *n-type* semiconductors or silicon-doped structures. The $\mathcal{P}_{p_x,p_x}(X,C)$ and $\mathcal{P}_{p_z,p_z}(X,C)$ values and observed trends are very similar to those calculated in the X structures: a decrease of the charge at the dopant side of the X-C bond causes a decrease of the band gap size. Moreover, $C_{X,C}$ values can still be used to distinguish between *p-type* and *n-type* structures if we use the $C_{X,C}$ of the

FIG. 20. Generalised band gap as a function of (a) $\mathcal{P}_{p_x, p_x}(X, C)$ and (b) $\mathcal{P}_{p_z, p_z}(X, C)$ in the X-C-X systems.

FIG. 21. Generalised band gap as a function of (a) $\mathcal{P}_{p_x, p_x}(X, C)$ and (b) $\mathcal{P}_{p_z, p_z}(X, C)$ in the X-C-X systems.

dopant in the nitrogen-doped systems which is the major contributor to the band of donor states located below the conduction band and not the average covalency.

E. X-V-X defect

a. Geometry analysis In the structures containing X-V-X defects (Figure 1d), each dopant coordinates three carbon atoms. Both dopants have identical or nearly identical local environments. In structures doped with a small dopant atom (B, N, P), the coordination polyhedra are essentially regular, as only one of the three X-C distances differs by $\sim 10^{-2}$ Å from the other two. On

the other hand, similarly to the X-V cases but to a lesser degree, large atoms are situated closer to the former position of the missing carbon; as a result, all three C-X-C bond angles are no longer equivalent. Consequently, one of the X-C distances is noticeably smaller than the other two (realising point group C_s , Figure 3f in the case of systems doped by Al or Si (~ 0.14 and ~ 0.08 Å, respectively)). This smaller X-C corresponds to a distance between dopant and carbon which is the most collinear with a dopant-to-dopant line. Similarly to the X-C-X case, when the local geometric environments of the two dopants are the same, the structures own the symmetries of the orthorhombic $Imm2$ (#44) space group, otherwise of the monoclinic Cm (#8) space group; moreover, structures doped by B, P and Si tend to be of higher symmetry than those doped by Al and N as for the X-C-X cases.

FIG. 22. Electronic band structures of (a) Al-, (b) B-, (c) N-, (d) P- and (e) Si-5-X-V-X systems, the red arrow connects k-points corresponding to the minimal-energy transition to the conduction band. The Fermi level is set to 0 eV.

b. Electronic structure analysis Unlike in some X-V systems (Al-, P and Si-doped), a vacancy located between two dopant atoms is maintained after the geometry relaxation of the X-V-X systems. The presence of a vacancy produces the highest amount of localised intermediate bands (IBs) among the considered systems. Their number increases with decreasing concentration, as a result of the separation of the dopant states from the conduction and valence band, and ranges between zero to three (B and Si, Figure 22). This is in a good agreement with results documented in literature (B [44], Si [45]). The relative position of the IBs depends on the atomic type of the dopant; however, the majority of IBs lie above the Fermi level, at variance with the X-V systems where the Fermi level is found above the majority of IBs. Due to this reason, the X-V-X systems realise the smallest band gaps of all considered cluster defects as we often find acceptor-like bands close to the conduction band minimum. The band structures of X-5-X-V-X systems are reported in Figure 22; we report the lowest considered concentration to show the highest number of IBs and energy gaps.

c. How to engineer width of the band gap As we mentioned previously, the X-V-X systems realise on average the smallest band gap size when compared to other defects, mostly due to the highest number of intermediate bands added to the energy gap of the pristine structure. Furthermore, all the systems with a non-null band gap show *p-type* behaviour, these being all the systems with a dopant concentration lower than 6.25 %. The importance of the effect of changing the dopant concentration on the width of the band gap depends significantly on the band structure of the specific system. This is due to the splitting of the bands from the conduction band, splitting of intermediate bands and due to how we measure the band gap. As an example, we can take a closer look at the boron-doped structures. The largest band gap in boron-doped systems is found at the largest dopant concentration, as all the added states lie at the bottom of the conduction band, this resulting in the single band gap (i.e., no intermediate bands); however, when we slightly decrease the concentration, the bands formed by the dopant split from the conduction band, creating an intermediate small band gap above them (section III A). When we continue to decrease the concentration, the dopant states move deeper towards the valence band, with a corresponding expected increase of the band gap size with the decrease of the dopant concentration. The band gap size varies by 1.6 eV (1.1 eV between 1.85 and 0.4 %) with the concentration, but this interval is much lower for the systems which have intermediate bands close to the bottom of the conduction band (Al, B). Hirshfeld charge analysis does not seem fruitful in finding a general trend even in the case of X-V-X structures; however, we can observe that the *p-type* dopants (Al, B) realise the smallest band gap and their Hirshfeld charges are between 0.04-0.11 a.u. Due to this, the resulting plot resembles a parabola (Figure 23b). Then we can conclude that the

FIG. 23. Generalised band gap as a function of Hirshfeld charges of the dopant's first neighbours (a) and of the dopant (b) in the X-V-X systems.

band gap size increases with the distance from this interval. Bond covalency seems to be a much better descriptor to tune the band gap size, as we observe that the band gap reduces drastically when the covalency decreases below -1.5 eV (Figure 24). We found a covalency threshold also in the case of X systems; however, the present case is notably different. In X systems, the covalency threshold was a means to distinguish between *p-* and *n-type* structures; in fact, we understood it in such a way that if we increase the bond covalency beyond a certain value, we start to observe the donor states close to the conduction band [56]. On the contrary, in X-V-X systems, when the covalency decreases below the -1.5 eV threshold, the acceptor states move towards the conduction band, thus reducing the band gap size. The $C_{X,C}$ values are similar to the X systems for the same dopant; thus, *n-type* dopants still correspond to the highest covalency values. Instead, now the situation is reversed: the *p-type* dopants form acceptor intermediate bands below the conduction band minimum, while *n-type* form acceptor intermediate bands in the middle of the pristine gap (Figure 22). In X-V-X configuration, the dopant neighbours are polarised very slightly, as the interval of $\mathcal{P}_{p_x,p_z}(C)$ values around zero has a width of just 3 %. We do not see any trend of the band gap width as a function of $\mathcal{P}_{p_x,p_z}(C)$. However, the $\mathcal{P}_{p_x,p_z}(C)$ values of the structures which do not realise a band gap near the Fermi level are closely packed around -1.35 %. By inspecting the dopant polarisation $\mathcal{P}_{p_x,p_z}(X)$, we observe that the situation is similar to the X-V system. The dopants with large atomic radii (Al, Si, P) show lower $\mathcal{P}_{p_x,p_z}(X)$ values than small atoms (B, N). However, as the smallest band gaps are realised by the *p-type* dopants (Al, B) and Si (0.4 % concentration) with very different atomic radius, there is no visible trend of the band as a function of $\mathcal{P}_{p_x,p_z}(X)$. We con-

FIG. 24. Generalised band gap as a function of the X-C bond covalency $C_{X,C}$ in X-V-X systems.

FIG. 25. Generalised band gap as a function of (a) $\mathcal{P}_{p_x, p_x}(X, C)$ and (b) $\mathcal{P}_{p_z, p_z}(X, C)$ in the X-V-X systems.

tinue by analysing the $\mathcal{P}_{p_x, p_x}(X, C)$ and $\mathcal{P}_{p_z, p_z}(X, C)$ polarisations. The observed trends are similar to the other defect types, the values near zero correspond to the *n-type* dopants. As we already established, to achieve a lower band gap we need to choose *p-type* dopant or Si; as a consequence, lower $\mathcal{P}_{p_x, p_x}(X, C)$ and $\mathcal{P}_{p_z, p_z}(X, C)$ correspond to the narrowest band gap. We would like to point out that Si experiences a drop in the band gap size in the lowest concentration, when one of the bands split from the conduction band.

We saw that the size of the band gap does not change monotonically with the change in the concentration of the defect. This is due to the splitting of intermediate bands from the conduction band when the concentration is reduced. We established that the easiest way to achieve a narrow band gap in X-V-X defects is to choose *p-type* dopant or Si. This was manifested by the lowest $C_{X,C}$, $\mathcal{P}_{p_x, p_x}(X, C)$ and $\mathcal{P}_{p_z, p_z}(X, C)$ values.

FIG. 26. Generalised band gap as a function of (a) $\mathcal{P}_{p_x, p_x}(X, C)$ and (b) $\mathcal{P}_{p_z, p_z}(X, C)$ in the X-V-X systems.

F. Character of the band gap

In our previous work [56], we attempted to find a general description which connects the directness of the band gap of the *p-type* systems to the specific parameter of the system. Our observations suggested that the directness did not depend on the dopant atomic type but solely on the size of the primitive unit cell. We saw that in all our systems, valence band maximum (VBM) was always located at Γ while the position of the conduction band minimum (CBM) was changing according to the multiplicity of the supercell (i.e. concentration of the dopant). As we substituted only a small fraction of the host matrix with the dopant we expected band folding to occur. With this assumption, we calculated where the CBM and VBM k -vectors of the primitive unit cell would be remapped in the supercell. VBM was always remapped in Γ ; therefore, when the CBM was remapped to (or closely to) Γ , we expected a direct band gap. This was indeed consistent with our observation, resulting in 1.85% and 0.4% concentration (corresponding to a multiplicity of 3 and 5 along all three axes) exhibiting a direct band gap.

In the present work, we indeed increase the concentration of the dopants in the equivalent supercell while the concentrations of the cluster defects remain the same. Therefore, we can expect the same rules to be in effect for the cluster defects in a more general manner, as now it is not the concentration of the dopant that dictates the size of the primitive unit cell but the concentration of the cluster defect. However, the situation is now less straightforward, as in many cases we do not observe just one band gap, and the dopant states are not exclusively added only to the top of the valence band or to the bottom of the conduction band. As a consequence, the directness of the measured band gap depends not only on the size of the system but also on which band gap about the Fermi

level is selected to measure the directness of the band gap. We observe that systems with the 1.85% and 0.4% concentration of cluster defect possess a direct energy gap between VBM and CBM if we define them as follows. As an uppermost band of the valence band, we consider the uppermost band with the negative (concave) curvature at Γ . This band is usually completely or partially empty and has the behaviour of an acceptor band as the band below 2 eV in Figure 27a. On the other hand, the lowermost band of the conduction band is the lowermost band with positive (convex) curvature. This is commonly a donor band which is fully or partially occupied, as it can be seen in Figure 27d right below the Fermi level. We here recall that to evaluate the band gap size, we measure the energy needed to provide the final electron jump to the conductive (delocalised) states in the conduction band. However, this jump can occur between either the localised valence (acceptor-like) or localised conduction (donor-like) bands and the conductive states of the conduction band. As a consequence, the band gap that we measure is not always the difference between VBM and CBM as we defined them above. Then, 3 scenarios can occur for *p-type* structures: *a*) direct energy gap coincides with our definition (Figure 27a), *b*) localised band representing the conductive state is located below the conduction band, whereas our measured band gap is indirect (Figure 27b), *c*) dopant adds valence (acceptor) states which are merged with the conduction band, then the band gap is indirect (Figure 27c). We notice that scenario *a*) is the most common in our systems, while *b*) and *c*) are rare exceptions. The *n-type* systems are characterised by adding occupied donor states at the bottom of the conduction band; in this case, we will always measure an indirect band gap (Figure 27d). This is caused by the fact that the donor band as well as the lowermost delocalised band of the conduction band have their minima located at Γ . Therefore, any minimal transition between the top of the donor band and the bottom of the delocalised band has to be indirect.

G. Design rules and technological applications

In this subsection, we focus on selecting the most promising candidate defects and dopants for different technological applications. We summarise the result of the selection in Table III.

1. Degenerate semiconductors

Degenerate semiconductors play a huge role in different fields of modern electronics. One of their most important quality is that they can be used as transparent conductive materials (TCMs), i.e. materials with sufficiently high electrical conductivity and visible light transparency. The large variety of possible applications of TCMs includes liquid crystal displays, photovoltaics,

FIG. 27. Electronic band structures of (a) P-3-X-V-X, (b) Si-5-X-C-X, (c) P-3-X-V and (d) P-3-X-C-X. The red arrow represents the measured band gap according to our definition (section III A) while the green arrow indicates the location of the direct band gap between the top of the valence band and the localised states of the conduction band. The Fermi level is set to 0 eV.

touchscreens, smart windows and electrodes [95, 96]. Moreover, the extreme properties of diamond (high carrier mobility, hardness, chemical inertness) favour its use in the above-mentioned applications. Indeed, transparent conductive boron-doped electrodes are already under intensive study and have been experimentally created and tested, especially for use in electrochemistry [97–99]. Current research on TCMs is mainly focused on solving two tasks: the first is to obtain a degenerate *p-type* semiconductor with better conductivity/carrier mobility and sufficiently large band gap (above 3.1 eV for visible light) [100, 101], while the second task focuses on designing an ultra-wide band gap semiconductor transparent for UV light [102]. Beyond the TCMs, degenerate semiconductors are used in tunnel diodes [103] and play a crucial role in achieving population inversion in solid-state lasers (laser diodes) [104] and superluminescent diodes [105].

If we consider potential applications of the material in optoelectronics and TCMs, we are interested in the

Application	Systems
Transparent conductive materials (LCDs, touchscreens, electrodes, lasers, tunnel diodes)	all concentrations: B-X, P-X B-X-C-X, P-X-X
	at conc. $\geq 1.85\%$: Al-X-C-X, Al-X, Al-X-V-X, Al-X-V, P-X-V, P-X-C-X, Si-X-V-X, B-X-X Si-X-V
Intermediate band photovoltaics, bioimaging agents	all X-V-X defects, B-X-V, N-X-V
Multi-colour emitters	all X-V-X defects, B-X-V, N-X-V, N-X-C-X, P-X-C-X, N-X-X, V
Optical filters	all defects with a band gap
<i>i-type</i> for PIN diodes	Si-X, Si-X-C-X, Si-X-X, Al-X-X, N-X-X

TABLE III. Table summarising promising candidates for different technological applications.

optical band gap of the material. In degenerate semiconductors, the optical (or apparent) band gap is widened by the width of the occupied (unoccupied) states in the conduction (valence) band of the *n-type* (*p-type*) semiconductor. This is called *Moss-Burstein shift* [106] and the size of the optical band gap is then equal to the energy required for the smallest possible direct transition between the valence band and an unoccupied state in the conduction band (*n-type*), or between the occupied states in the valence band and the bottom of the conduction band (*p-type*). At the largest concentration (6.25 %), in some of our systems (B-, P-X-V, Al-, P-, Si-X-V-X) the energy gap near the Fermi level is completely closed by the dopant states; these structures will not be considered in the following discussion as the energy gap is essential for applications in optoelectronics and TCMs. Nevertheless, they still constitute degenerate semiconductors and can be used as electrodes. We stress that all considered degenerate semiconductors, except the above-mentioned with no gap, have a single energy gap about the Fermi level. Intermediate bands in the degenerate semiconductor would indeed increase its optical absorption.

The most effective way to achieve *p-type* degenerate diamond is to dope it with boron in the X or X-C-X dopant configuration as the degeneracy is achieved even at the lowest simulated concentrations (0.4 %). For X-C-X systems it is in agreement with the PDOS analysis suggesting that the carbon between two dopants plays the major role in causing *p-type* degeneracy (section III A). The 1.85 % concentration seems to be crucial for the

FIG. 28. Optical band gap of the degenerate *p-type* (a) and *n-type* (b) diamonds.

non-degenerate to degenerate transition, as at this concentration the number of degenerate systems increases significantly (see Figure 28). Then, as expected, using *p-type* dopant atomic types (Al, B) increases the probability of achieving degeneracy. When the cluster defect consists of a dopant and a vacancy, the situation is more complicated, as the dopant states do not form a compact band but are spread within the band gap. Due to this spread, B-doped structures do not realise *p-type* degeneracy, while systems doped with *n-type* dopants (N, P) or the isovalent Si at larger concentrations do. In the degenerate Al and B doped cases, we observe the highest positive and the most concentration dependent dopant $\mathcal{P}_{p_x, p_z}(X)$ polarisation and the lowest X-C bond covalency $C_{X,C}$. On the other hand, the degenerate *n-type* diamond can be obtained solely by phosphorus doping; this is obtained in all simulated concentrations, when the dopant configuration was X or X-X and once in the X-C-X configuration in the highest concentration. Therefore, it seems that placing any kind of defect other than another phosphorus atom close to the dopant reduces the potential for creating a degenerate *n-type* diamond. In clear contrast to aluminium and boron, degenerate structures doped by phosphorus are characterised by the lowest $\mathcal{P}_{p_x, p_z}(X)$, $\mathcal{P}_{p_x, p_z}(C)$, $\mathcal{P}_{p_x, p_x}(X, C)$, $\mathcal{P}_{p_z, p_z}(X, C)$ polarisations and high covalency $C_{X,C}$ values. Therefore, we may conclude that the extremes of the above-mentioned descriptor values lead to either *p-type* or *n-type* degeneracy in certain defect types.

We report the widths of the optical band gap of all degenerate systems in Figure 28. We observe that an increase in the dopant concentration widens the optical band gap of both, *p-type* and *n-type* systems with the single exception being the Al-X case. Therefore, the width of the Moss-Burstein shift increases to a greater degree than the size of the energy gap between the va-

lence and conduction band decreases with the increase of the dopant concentrations. *p-type* systems generally display wider band gaps, especially for boron-doped structures (X, X-C-X) reaching above 5 eV for the highest concentration. The band gap width of the *n-type* systems reaches above 4.5 eV at the highest concentration, while the systems doped by single phosphorus atom (X) seem to manifest the largest band gaps. The only exception corresponds to the X-C-X system; however, the X-C-X defect forms a degenerate semiconductor only at 6.25% concentration. Such large energies correspond to the UV light up to the UV-C wavelengths and as DFT tend to underestimate band gap size, they are probably even larger. However, we may expect a decrease in transparency due to the intraband transitions [107]. By analysing the density of states, we expect that this affects mostly structures with cluster defects at high doping concentrations. The intraband absorption can be reduced by lowering dopant concentrations due to the fewer electrons (holes) available in the conduction (valence) band; this, however, at the cost of reduced conduction. Nevertheless, we expect the majority of the defect-related absorption to be in the infrared wavelengths and the visible/UV transparency to be not affected significantly.

The final selection of the material is therefore a tradeoff between conductivity and transparency and depends on the specific application. We may conclude that if transparency is the most important feature for the selected application, then structures doped by boron and phosphorus in X configuration are the most promising options. On the other hand, if the target application requires high conductivity and lower transparency to visible light is not an issue, cluster defects in high concentrations should be selected. Moreover, even in cases with high conductivity, the UV transparency of the diamond should be preserved [108].

2. Semiconductors with intermediate bands (IB)

One of the suggested advanced photovoltaic technologies to overcome the Shockley and Queisser limit of the single band gap solar cell [109] are the intermediate band solar cells (IBSC). In the single band gap solar cell, the significant part of the spectrum is either not absorbed (energies below the band gap) or is not efficiently utilised due to carrier thermalisation (energies above the band gap). Introducing IBs into the band gap by deep-level impurities can increase the absorption of photons with energy lower than the original band gap, as the IBs act as stepping stones on the way to the conduction band. Moreover, high-energy photons are harvested more optimally as now it is possible to use wide band gap semiconductors [110–114]. The same principle of photon up-conversion seems promising for the design of the contrast agents which eliminates the necessity of using UV light in photoluminescence spectroscopy. This would significantly reduce the photodamage and increase the depth of

penetration in bioimaging [115, 116]. In addition, IB materials can serve as multicolour electroluminescent emitters [117, 118]; with suitable control of which interband transition occurs, it might be possible to control the mixing of colours to achieve the desired output colour [119]. This combined with the certain sizes of the energy gaps would make it possible to create white LED with simple construction.

We now inspect our systems containing IBs from the point of view of reducing the spectral losses, thus, increasing the cell efficiency. For simple analysis, we use four parameters: the number, average size and standard deviation of the energy gaps as well as the average width of the IBs. The standard deviation s_N of the energy gap sizes is calculated as

$$s_N = \sqrt{\frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N (x_i - \bar{x})^2} \quad (9)$$

where x_i are the sizes and \bar{x} is the arithmetic average of the energy gaps of the studied system while N is the number of the energy gaps. The standard deviation is a measurement of the dispersion of considered values; in our case, it conveniently helps us to understand the relative positions of the IBs in the former band gap. Our ultimate goal is to find the most promising candidates for the above-mentioned applications; thus, the most significant parameter is the number of energy gaps, as each added energy gap increases possible options for transition. The second criterion is to find a balance between the average size and standard deviation, the higher standard deviation is preferred to increase the spectral absorption; however, if one of the energy gaps is too large (large average and standard deviation) significant part of the solar spectrum will not be utilised. Furthermore, IBs with smaller widths are prioritised to decrease the intraband absorption [120]; however, a low number of energy gaps and narrow IBs result in large energy gaps.

By inspecting Figure 29a, we immediately notice that more than two energy gaps appear only in the X-V systems, while four gaps appear only in systems with X-V-X (B, Si) cluster defects. To achieve three energy gaps with X-V defect, we need structures in which vacancy still exists (B, N), i.e. dopant is not forming a regular octahedron with its carbon neighbours; this can be achieved by doping with a dopant with a small atomic radius. As we discussed in the previous subsections (section III A, section III E), by decreasing the dopant concentration we split defect bands, thus, forming more energy gaps until all bands are split and the number of energy gaps saturates. We proceed by considering the average size and the standard deviation of the energy gaps (Figure 29b). We observe that X-V structures are again divided into two groups according to their dopant environment. X-V doped by large dopants (Al, P, Si), many X-X (Al, B) and X (Al, N) structures possess large average band gap width as well as large standard deviation; this indicates that the defect state is located close to the conduc-

tion or valence band with one of the energy gaps being significantly larger. We may conclude that these materials will not be suitable for the IBSC, as the larger energy gap tends to be above 3 eV; however, they still might be promising as semiconductor optical absorption filters for specific applications, e.g. simultaneous filtering of the part of the IR spectrum and all of the UV light [121]. The materials with a vacancy (V), X-C-X defect (N, P) and X-X (N) show large average energy gap widths and low standard deviation values while realising only two energy gaps. This means that the bands formed by the defect states are located near the middle of the band gap; such systems achieve higher absorption efficiencies than the above-mentioned systems, especially when doped in high concentration to decrease the sizes of the gaps. However, due to the two large energy gaps with the sizes corresponding to the energies of the visible light, these structures have a bigger potential of being used as multicolour emitters rather than as IBSC. The last group of systems owns average energy gap values around 1 eV and lower standard deviations. These are mostly systems containing vacancy and a dopant, X-V doped by dopants with small atomic radii (B, N) and X-V-X structures. The X-V structures (B, N) and X-V-X structures doped by Al and N still contain one relatively large gap (>1.5 eV) when doped in lower concentrations; nonetheless, three energy gaps provide many options for possible transitions. The remaining structures (B-, P-, Si-X-V-X) represent the most promising candidates for IBSC materials as they possess the largest number of energy gaps, being at least one of the energy gaps under 0.5 eV while there is no larger energy gap than 1.5 eV; therefore, the solar spectrum can be utilised in the most efficient manner. The last considered parameter, the average IB width for each defect type and three lower concentrations is reported in Figure 29c). As expected, with lowering concentration the bands become more localised, which corresponds to a decrease of the IB width. We recall that wide IBs decrease the efficiency because of the intraband transitions; to avoid this effect, it is more efficient to choose a low concentration of the dopant.

In this subsection, we analysed IB materials to estimate their potential for maximizing solar spectral absorption. We observed that the promising candidates for the IBSCs are the structures doped by cluster defects consisting of both, dopant(s) and a vacancy, while X-V-X systems doped by B, P and Si seem to utilise the solar spectrum most efficiently. The increase of defect concentration can help in decreasing the sizes of the energy gaps of the X-V (B, N), X-C-X (N, P), X-X (N) and V systems, at the cost of the increase of the width of the IBs. The IB structures with a very wide energy gap are the least suitable for the photon upconversion applications, this includes systems doped by X (Al, N), X-V (Al, P, Si) and X-X (Al, B). Nevertheless, all IB structures might be useful for specific applications such as multicolour emitters or optical filters, where emitting or blocking certain wavelengths is desired.

FIG. 29. Average energy gap as a function of the number (a) and the standard deviation of the energy gaps (b). The values in the plot (a) are intentionally spread around integer numbers corresponding to the number of the energy gap for better readability; the discrete coloured regions correspond to different numbers of energy gaps. The average IB width as a function of the dopant concentration is represented in (c).

3. Semiconductor type and activation energies

In this subsection, we will analyse which of the studied systems are *p-type*, *n-type* or if they show *intrinsic-like* (or *i-type*) behaviour; then, we will qualitatively examine the effect of the different dopants and cluster defects on the activation energy. In the following discussion, we focus on the lower concentrations of the defect, where observed features (e.g. positions of the impurity bands) do not change so rapidly with the change of the concentration. Therefore, we do not expect these trends to change even at lower concentrations than simulated. We acknowledge that the number of carriers in structures with deep impurities would be very low under standard conditions; however, the defect can still be classified as *p-type* or *n-type* even with low conductivity of the material. We are also aware that this description is based on the assumption that a defect classification as *p-* or

n-type translates directly into the material conductivity type. However, in real materials, the presence of different impurities and external stimuli can lead to charge compensation effects, where the formation of charged defects may reduce the number of free carriers and alter the expected electrical behaviour (see section II). Therefore, even if the defect is nominally *p-* or *n-type*, the overall electrical behaviour of the material may differ from this idealised classification. A more rigorous analysis of how defects influence conductivity would require calculating ionisation energies to determine the stability of different charge states at various Fermi levels [75]. Our distinction between types is based on the band structure and the position of the Fermi level in the following way [81]:

1. *p-type*. The band structure is characterised by a completely or partially empty impurity band located in the band gap or merged with the valence band; if the impurity band is only partially empty, then it is closer to the valence than to the conduction band, i.e. it is energetically favourable to promote an electron from the valence band to the impurity band than to promote an electron from the impurity band to the conduction band. Moreover, the shape of the impurity band can indicate if it originates from the valence or the conduction band (negative curvature at Γ , see Figure 27a).
2. *n-type*. The band structure is characterised by a completely or partially full impurity band located in the band gap, or merged with the conduction band; if the impurity band is only partially full, then it is closer to the conduction than to the valence band, i.e. it is energetically favourable to promote an electron from the impurity band to the conduction band than to promote an electron from the valence band to the impurity band. Moreover, the shape of the impurity band can indicate if it originates from the valence or the conduction band (positive curvature at Γ , see Figure 27d).
3. *i-type*. The band structure is characterised by a large energy gap between the fully occupied impurity band located close to the valence band and the nearest unoccupied band in the conduction band (see Figure 7a-b). These systems behave as *intrinsic* semiconductors.

As mentioned in the previous subsections, *p-type* dopants (Al, B) usually form *p-type* semiconductors while *n-type* dopants (N, P) usually form *n-type* semiconductors as expected. However, there are a few exceptions to this rule. *n-type* dopants can form *p-type* structures if a vacancy is part of the cluster defect. Moreover, both *p-type* and *n-type* dopants can form structures which show behaviour characteristic for *intrinsic* (i.e. *i-type*) semiconductors; this was observed in the X-X systems where two neighbouring Al atoms and two neighbouring N atoms seem to compensate for each other. In the majority of the cases, the isovalent dopant Si forms *i-type*

FIG. 30. Electronic band structures of the Al-4-X-X structure additionally doped by (a) Al and (B) N, the red arrow connects k-points corresponding to the minimal-energy transition to the conduction band. The Fermi level is set to 0 eV.

structures, with the exception of the systems containing a vacancy (X-V and X-V-X) systems which are *p-type* semiconductors. The *i-type* systems are promising candidates for co-doping, as introducing another impurity to the structure (e.g. Al or N), can determine if the structure will be *p-type* or *n-type*. Furthermore, introducing different types of impurities can tune the edges of the valence and conduction bands, thus the band gap, as well as increase the number of intermediate bands in the former band gap [122]. As an example, we indeed doped a few insulating structures with single Al and N dopants located equidistantly between the original defects, i.e. as far from them as possible. By calculating the optimised geometry and the band structures, we proved the above-mentioned assumptions and two of the band structures are reported in Figure 30. We report all the studied systems divided into categories based on their type of conductivity in Table IV.

Another extremely important quantity for technological applications is the activation energy of the dopant. The activation energy indicates the amount of free carriers, thus conductivity, at a given temperature. Therefore, for the majority of the applications, it is necessary to dope the semiconductor with defects with sufficiently low activation energies to obtain adequate conductivity at room temperature [75, 123]. The task of obtaining shallow defect levels corresponding to low activation energies in the case of the wide band gap semiconductors is especially difficult [122]. The *p-type* diamond has been successfully created with relatively low activation energies with boron doping [124], while achieving useful *n-type* doping is still a significant challenge [125]. Doping by phosphorus seems to be the most promising sin-

X	<i>p-type</i>	<i>n-type</i>	<i>i-type</i>
Al	X, X-V		X-X
	X-C-X		
	X-V-X		
B	X, X-V		
	X-C-X		
	X-V-X, X-X		
N	X-V	X	X-X
	X-V-X	X-C-X	
P	X-V	X, X-C-X	
	X-V-X	X-X	
Si	X-V		X, X-C-X
	X-V-X		X-X
V	X		

TABLE IV. Table dividing systems into categories based on the type of conductivity.

gle donor dopant; however, high dopant concentrations are required to obtain shallow impurity levels [19]. This problem has been tackled by many ab initio studies focused on codoping [77, 126–128]. To this aim, we attempt to order different types of defects based on their activation energies irrespective of the concentration; we recall that all the assumptions in this subsection are meant for low concentrations. Our qualitative analysis is mostly based on the depth of the dopant states in the band gap. In a few cases, we observe inconclusive results, e.g. two types of defects form a degenerate semiconductor even at the lowest concentration. We then decide by analysing the density of states; we inspect which system’s impurity band has a higher chance of detaching from the valence (conduction) band when the concentration is further reduced. As an example, we proceed as follows. We observe that the B-X defect forms a degenerate semiconductor while the B-X-X defect forms a band of acceptor states 0.7 eV above the valence band at the same concentration; therefore, we conclude that the B-X defect has a lower activation energy than the B-X-X defect. The exact activation energies would require significantly more calculations, such as considering structures with charged defects and their formation energies [75], and are beyond the scope of this work. Our findings are reported in [Table V](#) from the largest to the smallest (left to right) activation energy for each dopant atom. We mark systems with the (p, n, i) labels corresponding to the type of the system (*p*-, *n*- or *i*-type), wherever it helps to highlight the contrast with other systems in the same row. The systems doped by N and P are both split into two rows to compare activation energies for *p*-type and *n*-type systems separately.

We observe that only a few defect cluster types can decrease the activation energy when compared to the single dopant case. The most prominent example is the X-C-X which decreases activation energy for both *p*-type dopants and for nitrogen-doped structure. However, in the case of

X	Activation energy (>)				
Al	X-X (<i>i</i>)	X-V-X	X-V	X	X-C-X
B	X-V	X-V-X	X-X	X	X-C-X
N(<i>p</i>)	X-V-X			X-V	
N(<i>n</i>)	X-X (<i>i</i>)	X		X-C-X	
P(<i>p</i>)	X-V-X			X-V	
P(<i>n</i>)	X-C-X	X-X		X	
Si	X	X-C-X	X-X	X-V-X(<i>p</i>)	X-V(<i>p</i>)

TABLE V. Table ordering systems according to their activation energy from the highest to the lowest (left to right) for each dopant atom. (p, n, i) labels correspond to the type of the system (*p*-, *n*- or *i*-type) and are added wherever they help to highlight the contrast with other systems in the same row. The systems doped by N and P are both split into two rows to compare activation energies for *p*-type and *n*-type systems separately.

N-X-C-X, the improvement was so small that both activation energies can be said to be equivalent; moreover, we do not see any improvement in the case of a phosphorus-doped structure which is far more interesting due to the shallower donor levels. On the other hand, the use of the X-X defects increases the depth of the impurity bands in all the cases, which in all the cases except for the isovalent silicon leads to the increase of the activation energy.

CONCLUSIONS

In this work, we attempted to uncover coupled structural-electronic features of different cluster defects formed by aggregation of dopant and/or vacancies. To this aim, we conducted a quantum mechanical investigation of four different defect types: *a*) dopant-vacancy complexes (X-V), *b*) two dopants as nearest neighbours (X-X), *c*) two dopants separated by one carbon atom (X-C-X) and *d*) two dopants separated by a vacancy (X-V-X). For each of these structures, we considered Al, B, N, P and Si as dopant atoms. The cluster defects were compared with the single dopant case (X) wherever relevant.

We saw that the dopant atomic radius has a crucial role in determining the local environment of the dopant in X-V complexes. The large dopant atoms (Al, P, Si) form octahedrons with their neighbours while the small dopants (B, N) form trigonal pyramidal configuration. In the case of other cluster defects, we very rarely found the change of point group characterising the local environment of the dopant with the change of the concentration or the dopant atomic kind. We saw that the number and positions of the intermediate bands (IBs) added to the former band gap of pristine diamond depends on the dopant atomic type as well as on the cluster defect type. The X-V doped by large atoms, X-X and X-C-X structures always add a single IB while X-V doped by small atoms and X-V-X defect add up to three IBs.

We found that irrespective of the type of the defect the *n-type* dopants realise the most covalent bonds of all studied dopants. This is true even in the case of structures containing vacancy which show *p-type* behaviour even when doped by *n-type* dopant. To achieve the smallest band gap with the X-V cluster we need to choose small dopant atoms; such atoms cause significant dominance of charge at the dopant site along one of the axes with respect to the other. When a small dopant atom is selected, we can decrease the band gap size even further by choosing a dopant which is an electron acceptor. Moreover, by comparing all structures containing a single *p-type* dopant atom, we were able to order the band gap sizes with respect to the coordination number (CN) of the dopant from widest to narrowest as follows: tetrahedral (CN=4), octahedral (CN=8) and trigonal pyramidal (CN=3) dopant coordination. The X-X structures often form more insulating structures than other defect types. This is caused by the self-compensation of the two dopants of the same atomic type and is the most apparent for Al and N which exhibit behaviour similar to the *intrinsic* semiconductors. On the other hand, P doped structure constitutes the degenerate semiconductor similarly to the X case. In X-X structures, the covalency, and orbital polarisations of the dopant and their neighbouring carbons seemed to be the promising parameters to engineer the desired band gap size. The positive band gap can be narrowed by the increase of the covalency as well as by the increase of the polarisation of the dopant and neighbouring carbons. *p-type* dopants in the X-C-X arrangement act in a very similar way to their counterparts in the X configuration. The best descriptor to tune band gap size in these systems is by charge redistribution along the X-C bond axis. We found that the increase of the charge at the dopant side of the bond increases the size of the band gap. We observed that the band gap width of X-V-X systems does not change monotonically with the change of concentration. This is a consequence of the splitting of the intermediate impurity bands from the conduction band. In these systems, the band gap size mostly depends on whether the dopant is of *p-* or *n-type*. The smallest band gaps are realised by *p-type* dopants and Si, which realise the most ionic bonds. How to achieve the directness of the band gap in diamond-based materials was extensively discussed in our previous work on structures doped with single dopant atoms. In this work, we found that the directness of the band gap depends solely on the multiplicity of the supercell (i.e., doping concentration) even in the case of cluster defects. However, due to the presence of multiple energy gaps about the Fermi level, this direct band gap is not always the band gap that we measured for our analysis.

In the last part of our work, we focused on technological applications of the cluster defects. We evaluated that the most promising dopants for transparent conductive materials are B (*p-type*) and P (*n-type*) in X configura-

tion and they realise optical band gaps corresponding to the UV-C wavelengths. If transparency is not a requirement, P-X-X (*n-type*) and B-X-C-X (*p-type*) defects can be used to increase the conductivity. By analysing the structures with IBs, we concluded that X-V-X systems doped by Si and B utilise the solar spectrum the most. This is due to the largest number of IBs and their optimal spacing in the band gap of the pristine diamond which maximises the optical absorption. Other IB structures may find their application in multicolour emitters and optical filters among others. Lastly, we analysed the depth of the impurity levels to determine dopant activation energies. Unfortunately, we did not find any defect configuration that would realise a much-needed decrease in the activation energy of *n-type* phosphorus when compared to its X configuration. In fact, the cluster defects seemed to increase the activation energy with respect to the X case in the majority of the cases. The only exceptions are X-C-X (Al, B, N) and all cluster defects of isovalent Si.

This work represents a set of suggestions on how to choose optimal dopant atomic types, their concentration and aggregation to achieve the desired electronic or optical properties. The last subsections are dedicated to several technological applications well suited for cluster defects. The reader is already presented with a variety of promising options for specific applications which can be promptly used in the design of particular devices.

AUTHOR CONTRIBUTIONS

All authors have contributed equally.

CONFLICTS OF INTEREST

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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